

Effect of MRP on yield. Mangalore, India, 1983-85.

Treatment	Yield (kg/plot)		
	1983	1984	1985
<i>Main plot</i>			
Application on day of transplanting	3.72	0.97	1.96
7 DBT	3.89	1.11	2.07
14 DBT	3.71	1.22	1.97
21 DBT	3.71	1.08	1.95
F test	ns	ns	ns
SEm ±	0.10	0.08	0.03
CV (%)	10.62	27.73	5.74
<i>Subplot</i>			
0 kg P/ha	3.10	1.13	1.89
13.2 kg P/ha	3.77	1.11	1.97
26.4 kg P/ha	4.46	1.09	2.07
39.6 kg P/ha	3.83	1.04	2.03
F test ^a	**	ns	**
SEm ±	0.10	0.05	0.02
CV (%)	10.59	17.58	4.50
Interaction (main × sub)	ns	ns	ns

^a*** = significant at 1% level, ns = not significant.

conducted during kharif seasons 1983-85. Experimental site soils are yellowish brown (10 YR 7/6 dry), clay loam, strong medium subangular blocky, dry hard, moist firm, wet sticky, moderately slow permeability with pH 5.7. They are high in organic C (1.26%) and available P (82 kg/ha), but low in available K (50 kg/ha).

Four main treatments (application at 0, 7, 14, and 21 d before transplanting [DBT]) and 4 subtreatments (0, 13.2, 26.4, and 39.6 kg P/ha) were tested in a split-plot design. All plots received 100 kg N and 73 kg K/ha.

Net plot (5.76 m²) yields over a period of 3 yr are presented in the table. Although the yield increase with MRP applied 7 DBT was not significant, the yield difference with 26.4 kg P/ha was significant. The interaction between P level and time of application was not significant. □

Weed seedlings transplanted with rice seedlings reduce grain yield

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We observed that grass weed seedlings had been transplanted with rice

seedlings in two farmers' fields in Guimba, Nueva Ecija, Philippines. We harvested 50 1-m² quadrats from areas in both fields where transplanted seedlings were contaminated with weed seedlings and 50 1-m² quadrats from areas where no weed seedlings had been transplanted.

In 1 field, yield from quadrats where an average of 29% of the hills were infested with *Echinochloa glabrescens*

was 372 g/m²; in areas where no weed seedlings were transplanted, the yield was 476 g/m². In the other field, yield from quadrats where an average 23% of the hills were infested with *Echinochloa oryzoides* was 434 g/m², 18% lower than the 530 g/m² yield where no infestation was observed.

Differences in yield between the weed-infested and weed-free hills were highly significant in both fields. □

Nitrogen sources and placement for irrigated rice

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We studied N source and placement method for irrigated rice on a clay loam soil with pH 8.3 and 0.6% organic matter.

Deep placement of urea supergranules (USG) gave a higher yield and was the

most efficient, but was not significantly different from incorporating urea in dry soil (see table). Efficiency of dry soil incorporation was on a par with deep placement of USG

Incorporating urea in puddled soil gave a significantly lower yield. Calcium ammonium nitrate incorporated in puddled soil had the lowest yield after control and was the least efficient. Yields were significantly higher with higher levels of fertilizer but fertilizer efficiency was higher at lower levels. □

Rice grain yield (variety IR6) and fertilizer efficiency as affected by different N sources and their methods of placement. Islamabad, Pakistan, 1982.

Treatment ^a	Grain yield ^b (t/ha)	Fertilizer efficiency (kg yield/kg N used)
Control	3.2 f	—
46 kg N/ha as urea incorporated in puddled soil (2/3 basal + 1/3 at PI)	5.0 d	41.2
46 kg N/ha as calcium ammonium nitrate incorporated in puddled soil (2/3 basal + 1/3 at PI)	4.6 e	30.9
46 kg N/ha as urea all incorporated in dry soil ^c	5.6 c	53.5
46 kg N/ha as USG deep placed, 4 DT	5.6 c	54.2
92 kg N/ha as urea incorporated in puddled soil (2/3 basal + 1/3 at PI)	5.6 c	26.4
92 kg N/ha as calcium ammonium nitrate applied in puddled soil (2/3 basal + 1/3 at PI)	5.1 d	21.7
92 kg N/ha as urea all incorporated in dry soil ^c	6.4 ab	35.7
92 kg N/ha as USG deep placed, 4 DT	6.6 a	37.6
SE	1.1	—

^aPI = panicle initiation, DT = days after transplanting. ^bMeans followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level of significance by DMRT. ^cThe field was irrigated and planted after dry soil incorporation.

Phosphorus application in acid-sulfate soil

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In the Cuu Long (Mekong) Delta of Vietnam, acid-sulfate soils are found in 1.15 million ha, mostly in Kien Giang, Long An, Dong Thap, Hau Giang, and An Giang Provinces. Seedling mortality and poor crop growth due to extremely

Effect of P application on agronomic characters, yield and yield components of lowland transplanted rice in acid-sulfate soils. Cuu Long Delta, Vietnam, 1983 wet season.

Method of P application	Rate (kg P/ha)	Seedling mortality (%)	Plant ht (cm)	Days to 50% heading	Lodging (1-9 scale)	Panicles/hill	Panicle length (cm)	Panicle wt (g)	Filled grains/panicle	Unfilled grains (%)	1000-grain wt (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Response to P (kg grain/kg P applied)
Control	0	39.6	95	107	1	4.2	17.5	1.43	30.5	33.6	31.6	0.96	
Full as basal	17.5	1.7	120	96	5	9.0	19.9	2.38	57.8	32.4	27.2	4.26	188.5
1/2 basal + 1/2 at 15 DT	17.5	1.8	120	97	3	8.9	20.0	2.16	54.3	38.5	28.5	3.92	169.1
1/2 at 15 DT + 1/2 at 30 DT	17.5	16.7	105	103	1	6.7	18.8	1.93	51.8	29.1	27.0	2.31	77.1
Full at 15 DT	17.5	11.1	109	102	1	7.2	19.0	1.80	46.5	33.4	28.3	2.85	108.0
Seedling root dipped in P slurry	17.5	3.1	115	100	3	9.6	18.9	1.90	51.7	35.2	28.1	4.12	180.5
Full as basal	26.2	1.2	125	96	5	9.2	19.5	2.08	53.3	34.5	27.9	4.11	180.0
CD (0.05)						1.6	1.2	0.20	11.3	5.6	2.6	0.55	
CV (%)						14.2	4.2	7.0	15.3	11.1	6.1	11.5	

low pH at planting and acute P deficiency are the major problems on these soils.

We conducted a field trial in the 1983 wet season to evaluate the effect on stand establishment and yield of methods of applying P. Seven treatments were tested in a randomized block design with four replications. The soil was clayey with 0.232% total N, 0.027% total P, 0.52% SO₄²⁻, 1.111 meq Al³⁺/100 g soil, and pH 3.7 at transplanting.

On 27 Jul 1983, we transplanted 38-d-old E425 seedlings spaced 20 × 15 cm. All plots received 80 kg N/ha as urea (30 kg N/ha basal + 20 kg N/ha 15 d after transplanting [DT] + 30 kg N/ha at 40 DT) and 20.5 kg K/ha as muriate of potash. P was applied as superphosphate (9% P).

A phosphate slurry was prepared by mixing superphosphate with soil and water in the ratio 1:1.5:2.5. Seedlings were dipped in slurry for 12 h before transplanting. About two-thirds of the slurry was consumed in treatment; the leftover was uniformly applied to the relevant plots to maintain a P level of 17.5 kg/ha.

In basal and split application, superphosphate was broadcast on the soil surface.

Missing hills were counted at panicle initiation. Lodging was scored on a 1-9 scale at maturity. The crop was harvested between 26 Oct and 8 Nov, depending on crop maturity in the different treatments.

Basal application, irrespective of quantity applied, resulted in lower seedling mortality (see table). It also appears to have augmented root development, increasing nutrient absorption.

Symptoms of P deficiency — narrow, short, and erect leaves with dirty dark green color and stunted plants with limited tillers — were high in control. Basal P enhanced tiller production and plant height and hastened crop maturity. That crop lodged moderately because of increased height and heavier panicles, but lodging did not affect grain yield.

At 17.5 kg P/ha, basal P resulted in significantly higher grain yield than other P application methods except seedling root dipped in phosphate slurry and split-applied P (1/2 basal + 1/2 at 15 DT). Basal application increased the yield mainly through increased number of panicles (higher survival of seedlings and more effective tillers/hill) and filled grains/panicle. Higher 1,000-grain weight in the absence of P might be attributed to reduced competition among fewer spikelets in the panicle.

Basal application of 17.5 kg P/ha resulted in maximum P efficiency. □

Effect of sulfur source and fertilizer on rice yield

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We studied the effect of S source and fertilizer on yield, verified earlier finding on applying 100 kg N/ha as urea with 1/2 t gypsum/ha, examined the effect of adding gypsum with the common farmer practice of 17:17:17 mixture and DAP, and separated the effects of Ca and S.

A 1980-81 kharif field trial involved 14 treatments in a randomized block design with 3 replications. Plot size was 24 m². Soil was sandy clay loam, pH 7.6, low soluble salts, EC 0.4 mmho/cm, with 273 kg N/ha, 7.32 kg P/ha, 292 kg

Grain and straw yields with different S fertilizers. Madurai, India, 1980-81 kharif.

Treatment ^a	Grain (t/ha)	Straw (t/ha)
Control	4.0	5.9
U 100 kg N/ha + CaO 27 kg/ha (20 kg Ca/ha)	4.3	6.6
AS 100 kg/ha alone	5.1	7.3
U 100 kg N/ha + elemental S 30 kg/ha	5.2	9.9
U 100 kg N/ha + elemental S 60 kg/ha	4.8	9.4
U 100 kg N/ha + G 250 kg/ha	5.4	10.9
U 100 kg N/ha + G 500 kg/ha	6.1	12.3
CaO 27 kg/ha alone (20 kg Ca/ha)	3.6	5.8
DAP 22 kg P/ha alone	4.0	6.9
TSP 22 kg P/ha alone	3.5	7.2
G 500 kg/ha alone	3.7	5.6
17:17:17 mixture	3.8	6.9
DAP + G 500 kg/ha	5.4	7.4
17:17:17 mixture + G 500 kg/ha	5.1	6.1
CD	0.4	0.3

^a U = urea, AS = ammonium sulfate, DAP = diammonium phosphate, G = gypsum, TSP = triple superphosphate.